

Compilation and Examination of the Existing Specialised Semantic Artefacts for the Earth System Sciences

Deliverable Report D2.1 of the Work Package 2 of the BITS Project

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1 Introduction

BITS¹ (BluePrints for the Integration Terminology Services in Earth System Sciences) aims to address a major remaining obstacle to the application of the FAIR data principles in Earth System Sciences (ESS), namely the inadequate encoding of semantics and data interoperability. BITS extended the existing Terminology Service² (TS) of the TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology³ to include the ESS collection for climate science and geoscientific collections (including curated objects from mineralogy, petrology and palaeontology). Since the start of BITS in July 2023, the TIB and the BITS project partners German Climate Computing Centre⁴ (DKRZ) and Senckenberg - Leibniz Institution for Biodiversity and Earth System Research⁵ (SGN) have been adding terminologies that are potentially useful for the ESS community. This report describes the status of the ESS collection at the end of June 2024. Throughout the report we use both the terms semantic artefacts and terminologies as umbrella terms for controlled vocabularies, thesauri, ontologies, etc.

One of the BITS tasks is to provide a synopsis of existing semantic artefacts and services that are useful for the ESS community, and to analyse their respective quality. In section 2, we list all services that host and/or display terminologies for the Earth System Sciences. In section (4), we describe all terminologies in the ESS collection. For the sake of completeness, section 5 also lists terminologies that have been proposed, but have not yet been included in the TIB TS.

¹<https://projects.tib.eu/bits/home>

²<https://terminology.tib.eu/ts>

³<https://www.tib.eu/en/>

⁴https://www.dkrz.de/en/dkrz-partner-for-climate-research?set_language=en

⁵<https://www.senckenberg.de/en/about-us/senckenberg-society-nature-research/>

2 Overview of Existing Relevant Terminology Services for the ESS

Semantic artefacts for the ESS can be found in many places: some (e.g. SWEET⁶ or ENVO⁷) are collected in special repositories for semantic artefacts (e.g. ESIP⁸, Bioportal⁹), some can be found in an institutional GitHub (e.g. PATO¹⁰), some don't have an open license (e.g. the CF Features¹¹), and some are not published in a machine readable and processable version, but have been mentioned in publications (e.g. ABCD-EFG¹²).

We have collected web addresses of existing terminology services that exclusively or partially host terminologies for the ESS (see tables 1 and 2). All services have human-readable web pages where terminologies and their corresponding terms can be searched. In addition, all services have either an API or a SPARQL endpoint where search can be performed also by machines.

Most portals specialise in specific research areas of the ESS, e.g. oceanography, or host terminologies from a specific community, e.g. ESIP (Earth Science Information Partners). Only the Earth Portal¹³ hosts the full range of ESS research domains. However, as it only displays terminologies hosted by them, the range of research areas covered is limited. TIB TS will grow to cover all research areas for the entire ESS community.

3 The Terminology Service of TIB

The TIB TS is a service under development, funded by several research projects, e.g. the German National Research Data Infrastructure¹⁴ NFDI (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur). It is based on the open software Ontology Lookup Service¹⁵ OLS, which is primarily designed for archiving and searching OWL ontologies, and to which the TIB has added an extension for ingesting simple SKOS vocabularies. The TIB TS is run, maintained and developed further by the so called OLS Team at TIB, whose members are mostly working for one of the projects.

The TIB TS consists of a central terminology service, sustainably maintained by the TIB, which hosts all the terminologies in its archive. It also contains collections of terminologies selected for specific research communities and maintained by related projects. Even though all changes to the central TIB TS must be discussed and approved by the OLS Team at TIB, all involved projects highly benefit from the development of the other projects for the TIB TS.

The TIB TS displays terminologies and makes them searchable, but it is not a long-term archive for terminologies. The majority of the terminologies in the TIB TS are developed and maintained by groups outside the TIB. To assure that all terminologies in the TIB TS fulfil certain quality standards, the TIB TS ensures quality control before a terminology is ingested. Right now, only the newest (ingestible) version of a terminology is shown. It is planned to archive also older versions of terminologies in the TIB TS in the future.

⁶<http://cor.esipfed.org/ont?iri=http://sweetontology.net/sweetAll>

⁷<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ENVO>

⁸<http://cor.esipfed.org>

⁹<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>

¹⁰<https://github.com/pato-ontology/pato/>

¹¹<https://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/ssnx/cf/cf-feature>

¹²<https://doi.org/10.7479/pwnr-sh74>

¹³<https://earthportal.eu/ontologies>

¹⁴<https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

¹⁵<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4>

There are a few quality criteria, which terminologies have to fulfill. A terminology can be ingested to the TIB TS if:

- it has an open license specified,
- it is available in a machine readable format (OWL¹⁶ or SKOS¹⁷),
- it has an identifier such as IRI¹⁸ or PURL¹⁹ and
- there are no errors, logical inconsistencies etc. in the terminology.

The OLS Team at the TIB has defined a schema for the mandatory and recommended metadata of terminologies²⁰, which can be tested with the corresponding SHACL file. This test has not yet been installed in the TIB TS and an investigation is currently being planned to see how many terms in the TIB TS fulfil these additional criteria.

Another (weaker) criterion for possible inclusion in the TIB TS is that a terminology should also be used by other research institutions and is regularly updated. Nevertheless, there are some terminologies in the services that haven't been updated for years because they describe small vocabularies, e.g. for the description of time²¹.

4 Terminologies in the ESS collection

With the beginning of BITS a new collection for Terminologies from the Earth System Sciences was established: the ESS collection. It can both be reached over the TIB TS²² and over NFDI4Earth²³.

At the BITS kick-off meeting on 12 October 2023 in Hanover it was decided that, initially, the BITS project members will select terminologies for the ESS collection. Therefore, project members collected a list of terminologies (N=57). Subsequently, the TIB performed quality tests for all proposed terminologies before they were ingested into the TIB TS. At the end of June 2024, there were 36 terminologies in the ESS collection of the TIB TS (see tables 3 and 4).

These terminologies can be sorted by topic according to table 5. The ESS collection contains 9 terminologies describing metadata and data structures, 3 terminologies describing physical units and 6 terminologies describing how data were produced, e.g. measurements or observations. The last group consists of terminologies that describe what has been measured or observed. However, this classification is not strict as there are terminologies, such as SWEET, which cover more than one of these topics.

Alternatively, terminologies can be sorted according to their Semantic Web standards and classified as ontologies or thesauri according to their semantic richness (see table 6). Only 3 of the 36 terminologies are in SKOS, all others are in OWL. However, 10 OWL terminologies are only hierarchical and are therefore thesauri rather than (expressive) ontologies and 23 are classified as ontologies. In some cases this classification may be questionable. Furthermore, the future versions of the thesauri may become semantically richer and the terminology may then be classified as an ontology.

Suggestions for additional terminologies can always be made by the ESS community. If these terminologies fulfil the quality criteria, are relevant to the ESS, and can be included in the TIB TS, they will be added to the ESS collection.

¹⁶Web Ontology Language <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

¹⁷Simple Knowledge Organization System <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

¹⁸Internationalized Resource Identifier

¹⁹Persistent Uniform Resource Locator

²⁰Susanne Arndt et al. (2024): <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11103071>

²¹<http://www.w3.org/2006/time>

²²<https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies?and=false&page=1&collection=ESS&sortedBy=title&size=10>

²³<https://terminology.nfdi4earth.de>

5 Suggested, but not ingested Terminologies

There were proposals for additional 21 terminologies (see tables 7 and 8). These terminologies could not be ingested by the TIB's OLS system due to a number of reasons. In the case of errors in the terminology itself, we have contacted the respective creators, as the OLS team does not modify terminologies created by others. The TIB will try again to include these terminologies on a regular basis.

The CF vocabularies in the table 8 cannot be ingested as they are highly connected SKOS vocabularies containing terms that have narrower/broader connections to terms in other vocabularies. TIB TS is designed for OWL ontologies and has the additional capability to ingest simple SKOS vocabularies. Unfortunately, these CF vocabularies cannot be ingested because of their complex relations. Due to the importance of the CF vocabulary to the ESS community, we are looking for ways to ingest these vocabularies nonetheless, either by simplifying relational structure and/or by ingesting them on a SKOSMOS server. This is work in progress and has not been completed yet.

6 Outlook

During the first year of the BITS project, the project team collected and analysed terminologies for the Earth System Science collection of the TIB TS. Our aim was to find terminologies that are relevant to the research areas for which data are stored in DKRZ's WDCC²⁴ and to the collections of SGN. This is work in progress and we will not stop looking for interesting terminologies.

Nevertheless, the question of quality has been considered only in a very limited way: all terminologies in the TIB TS are semantically correct, and there will be tests for a standardised set of metadata in the future. On the other hand, users of the TIB TS will want more information to decide whether a particular terminology is useful for their specific needs. Our future work will be to derive further quality criteria that can be displayed with the terminologies.

²⁴<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/>

Name	Website	Description	Comments
Agroportal	https://agroportal.lirmm.fr	The AgroPortal project aims to offer a reference ontology repository for agronomy.	OntoPortal instance. FAIR score, version control, metrics, mappings, annotator, recommender, widgets.
BioPortal	https://biportal.bioontology.org/	Repository of biomedical ontologies	OntoPortal instance. Metrics, mappings, semantic difference between versions, widgets.
BODC's vocabularies	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/vocabularies/	Server of the British Oceanographic Data Centre at the National Oceanography Centre (NOC), which also hosts the NERC Vocabulary Server. It provides access to lists of standardised terms that cover a broad spectrum of disciplines of relevance to the oceanographic and wider community.	
CGI Vocabularies Register	http://geosciml.org/resource/def/voc/	Managed by the IUGS Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information (CGI). Hosts terminologies for geosciences.	Vocabularies are also published at the Research Vocabularies Australia portal.
EarthPortal	https://earthportal.eu/ontologies	Developed within the European FAIR-IMPACT project. Semantic artefacts for Earth sciences can be uploaded and searched.	OntoPortal instance. FAIR score, version control, metrics, mappings, annotator, recommender, widgets.
EcoPortal	https://ecportal.lifewatch.eu/	LifeWatch ERIC repository of semantic resources for ecology and related domains	FAIR scores, metrics, mappings, widgets.
ESIP COR	http://cor.esipfed.org/ont#/	Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) community ontology repository	Not all terminologies are open and have specified licenses.
GFBio	https://terminologies.gfbio.org/	The GFBio Terminology Service helps to connect through a single access point to various kinds of terminologies in the biological domain in a uniform and transparent manner.	Metrics, widgets
International Virtual Observatory Alliance	https://ivoa.net/rdf/	The Virtual Observatory (VO) is the vision that astronomical datasets and other resources should work as a seamless whole. The International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA) is an organisation that debates and agrees the technical standards that are needed to make the VO possible.	Only RDF vocabularies
Linked Earth landing page	http://linked.earth/ontology/	6 Vocabularies for annotating paleoclimatology data, methods, and datasets	Only RDF vocabularies.
Linked Open Vocabulary (LOV)	http://liveschema.eu/organization/lov	LOV's main initial objective was to help publishers and users of linked data and vocabularies to assess what was available for their needs, to reuse it as far as possible, and to insert their own vocabulary production seamlessly in the ecosystem.	All Fields of Science

Table 1: Overview of existing Terminology Collections and Services for the ESS

Name	Website	Description	Comments
LOTERRRE	https://www.loterre.fr/presentation/	Platform for multidisciplinary terminological scientific resources sharing, complying with the linked open data standards and the FAIR principles.	All Fields of Science
Marine Metadata Interoperability Ontology Registry and Repository	https://mmisw.org/ont#/	The current content of the NVS is predominantly targeted at the oceanographic and associated domains.	
NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/	The current content of the NVS is predominantly targeted at the oceanographic and associated domains.	SKOS version of Climate and Forecast Conventions vocabularies.
Orbital-Space-Ontology-Project	https://github.com/dataONEorg/sem-prov-ontologies	Collection of 8 Space Domain Modelling Ontologies at GitHub. Ontologies focused on scientific observations and scientific workflow provenance.	Not open
Research Vocabularies Australia	https://vocabs.arcd.edu.au/vocabs/page/about	Covers a broad spectrum of research fields - across health and medicine, sciences, social sciences, arts and humanities.	Widgets. Several licenses, only some open.
Semantics and Provenance Ontologies	https://github.com/DataONEorg/sem-prov-ontologies	GitHub with 5 community developed and maintained ontologies for concepts needed for earth observations data and workflow processes.	Made for MOSAIC experiment

Table 2: Extension of Table 1: Overview of existing Terminology Collections and Services for the ESS

Abbreviation	Name	Link	Description
abcd	ABCD Base Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/abcd	The base ontology of the ABCD Standard.
bco	The Biological Collections Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/bco	The BCO supports the interoperability of biodiversity and biodiversity related data, including data on museum collections, environmental/metagenomic samples, and ecological surveys.
bk	Basisklassifikation	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/bk	German decimal classification system based on the Dutch Basic Classification (NBC)
chebi	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/chebi	A dictionary of molecular entities focused on 'small' chemical compounds.
chrono	Darwin Core Chronometric Age Extension vocabulary	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/chrono	Vocabulary for the Darwin Core Chronometric Age Extension
dfgfo	DFG Classification of Subject Areas Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/dfgfo	DFG Fachsystematik Ontology / DFG Classification of Subject Areas Ontology (DFGFO)
dpv	Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/dpv	Terms to describe and represent information related to processing of personal data based on established requirements such as for the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
dsw	Darwin Semantic Web	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/dsw	Darwin Core Terms
duo	The Data Use Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/duo	DUO is an ontology which represent data use conditions.
dwc	Darwin Core main vocabulary	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/dwc	Darwin Core terms suitable for use with both literal and IRI values
ecso	The Ecosystems Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/ecso	DataONE ontology of Carbon Flux measurements for MsTMIP and LTER Use Cases
edam	Bioinformatics operations, data types, formats, identifiers and topics	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/edam	Concepts that are prevalent within bioinformatics, including types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations and topics.
efo	Environmental Factor Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/efo	The scope of EFO is to support the annotation, analysis and visualization of data handled by many groups at the EBI and as the core ontology for OpenTargets.org
envo	The Environment Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/envo	ENVO is an ontology which represents knowledge about environments, environmental processes, ecosystems, habitats, and related entities.
envthes	Environmental Thesaurus	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/envthes	Thesaurus for long term ecological research, monitoring, experiments
ets	Ecological Trait-data Standard	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/ets	Terms for the use in datasets containing quantitative and qualitative functional traits
foaf	Friend of a Friend (FOAF) vocabulary	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/foaf	The Friend of a Friend (FOAF) RDF vocabulary.
gemet	General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/gemet	GEMET has been developed as an indexing, retrieval and control tool for the European Topic Centre on Catalogue of Data Sources (ETC/CDS) and the European Environment Agency (EEA).
geosparql	GeoSPARQL Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/geosparql	An RDF/OWL vocabulary for representing spatial information
gndo	Gemeinsame Normdate	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/gndo	Gemeinsame Normdatei (Integrated Authority File) offers a broad range of elements to describe authorities.

Table 3: Overview of Terminologies in the ESS collection, Part 1.

Abbreviation	Name	Link	Description
oboe	The Extensible Observation Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/oboe	OBOE is a formal ontology for capturing the semantics of scientific observation and measurement.
om	Ontology Units of Measure 2.0	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/om	OM models concepts and relations important to scientific research. It has a strong focus on units, quantities, measurements, and dimensions.
pato	PATO - the Phenotype And Trait Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/gndo	An ontology of phenotypic qualities (properties, attributes or characteristics).
po	Plant Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/po	An ontology that describes plant anatomy, morphology, and growth and development in plants.
prov	The PROV Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/prov	PROV-O provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to represent and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts.
sbo	Systems Biology Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/sbo	Terms commonly used in Systems Biology, and in particular in computational modeling.
schemaorg	Schema.org Vocabulary	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/schemaorg	Machine readable representation of vocabularies that cover entities, relationships between entities and actions.
sio	Semanticscience Integrated Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/sio	SIO provides a simple, integrated ontology of types and relations for rich description of objects, processes and their attributes.
sosa	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/sosa	This ontology is based on the SSN Ontology by the W3C Semantic Sensor Networks Incubator Group (SSN-XG), together with considerations from the W3C/OGC Spatial Data on the Web Working Group.
ssn	Semantic Sensor Network Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/ssn	This ontology describes sensors, actuators and observations, and related concepts.
stato	The Statistical Methods Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/stato	STATO contains concepts and properties related to statistical methods, probability distributions and other concepts related to statistical analysis, including relationships to study designs and plots.
sweet	Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology Ontologies	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/sweet	SWEET is a highly modular ontology suite with 6000 concepts in 200 separate ontologies covering Earth system science.
time	Time Ontology in OWL	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/time	Description of date and time structured with separate values for the various elements of a calendar-clock system. The temporal reference system is fixed to Gregorian Calendar.
to	Plant Trait Ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/to	An ontology that describes phenotypic traits in plants. Each trait is a distinguishable feature, characteristic, quality or phenotypic feature of a developing or mature plant.
uat	Unified Astronomy Thesaurus	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/uat	UAT is a thesaurus which unifies existing, divergent, and isolated controlled vocabularies in astronomy and astrophysics.
uo	Units of measurement ontology	https://terminology.tib.eu/ts/ontologies/uo	Metrical units for use in conjunction with PATO.

Table 4: Overview of Terminologies in the ESS collection, Part 2.

Classificaton	Terminologies	Number of Terminologies
Basic Ontologies for describing data, structures etc.	bk, dfgfo, dpv, duo, dwc, foaf, gndo, prov, schemaorg	9
Ontologies for describing physical units	om, time, uo	3
Ontologies for describing measurements/observations, areas	geosparql, sosa, ssn, oboe, uat, stato	6
Environmental/Biological Ontologies	abcd, bco, chebi, chrono, dsw, eco, edam, efo, envthes, ets, gemet, pato, po, sbo, sio, sweet, to	18

Table 5: Topics of the Terminologies in the ESS collection.

Terminology	OWL/ SKOS	O = Ontology/ T = Thesaurus
abcd	OWL	O
bco	OWL	O
bk	OWL	T
chebi	OWL	O
chrono	OWL	T
dfgfo	OWL	T
dpv	SKOS	T
dsw	OWL	T
duo	OWL	O
dwc	OWL	T
eco	OWL	O
edam	OWL	O
efo	OWL	O
envthes	SKOS	T
ets	OWL	T
foaf	OWL	T
gemet	OWL	T
geosparql	OWL	T
gndo	OWL	O
oboe	OWL	O
om	OWL	O
pato	OWL	O
po	OWL	O
prov	OWL	O
sbo	OWL	T
schemaorg	OWL	O
sio	OWL	O
sosa	OWL	O
ssn	OWL	O
stato	OWL	O
sweet	OWL	O
time	OWL	O
to	OWL	O
uat	SKOS	T
uo	OWL	O

Table 6: Semantic Web Standards of Terminologies in the ESS collection.

Acronym	Name	Link	Terminology Language	Description	Reason for failed ingestion
ABCD-EFG	Access to Biological Collection Data Extended for Geosciences	https://efg.geocase.eu/efg		The Extension for Geosciences (EFG) extends the ABCD schema to integrate geological data, including information about paleontological and geological collection items	OWL/SKOS version of ontology has not yet been provided.
AO	Annotation Ontology	https://code.google.com/archive/p/annotation-ontology/source/default/source	OWL	An open ontology for annotating scientific documents on the web	Errors in terminology.
FLOPO	Flora Phenotype Ontology	https://github.com/flora-phenotype-ontology/flopoontology	OWL		Errors in terminology.
GAZ	Gazeteer	http://environmentontology.github.io/gaz/	OWL	A gazetteer constructed on ontological principles. The countries are actively maintained.	Errors in terminology; see https://github.com/EnvironmentOntology/gaz/issues
GCMD	Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Keywords	https://wiki.earthdata.nasa.gov/display/CMR/MASA+GCMD+keywords		Hierarchical set of controlled Earth Science vocabulary.	Not machine-readable.
GTS	Geological Timescale Model	https://github.com/CGI-IUGS/timescale-ont	OWL	Representation of the GeoSciML Geologic Timescale model, compatible with geospatial information transfer standards.	Errors in terminology.
GeoNames	GeoNames ontology	https://www.geonames.org/ontology/ontology_v3.3	OWL	The GeoNames Ontology makes it possible to add geospatial semantic information to the World Wide Web.	Errors in terminology.
NCBITAXON	National Center for Biotechnology Information Organismal Classification	http://pur1.obolibrary.org/obo/ncbitaxon.owl	OWL	Curated classification and nomenclature for all of the organisms in the public sequence databases.	Very large ontology, ingestion declined 2022. New request for ingestion.
ODM2	ODM2 Controlled Vocabularies	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/api/v1/actiontype/?format=skos	SKOS	Information model for spatially discrete, feature-based earth observations that is aimed at data interoperability.	Errors in terminology.
QUDT	QUDT CATALOG - Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Data Types Ontologies	https://www.qudt.org/2.1/catalog/qudt-catalog.html	OWL	Set of vocabularies representing the various quantity and unit standards.	Errors in terminology.

Table 7: Suggested but not yet ingested Terminologies in the ESS collection, Part 1.

Acronym	Name	Link	Terminology Language	Description	Reason for failed ingestion
CF-Parameter	Climate and Forecast (CF) Standard Names	https://mmisw.org/ont/cf/parameter	SKOS	Ontology representation of the Climate and Forecast (CF) standard names parameter vocabulary	License was not explicitly stated.
P07	Climate and Forecast Standard Names	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/	SKOS	Climate and Forecast Standard Names. Interlinked to the following vocabularies over broader/narrower term relation. Has to be ingested first.	Ingestion failed because TIB TS cannot ingest SKOS vocabularies with relations to separate vocabularies.
P01	BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/	SKOS	Terms which describe individual measured phenomena.	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved
P02	SeaDataNet Parameter Discovery Vocabulary	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02/current/	SKOS	Terms describing measurement phenomena	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved
P06	BODC-approved data storage units	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/	SKOS	Terms to describe the measurement units for data.	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved
P29	Climate and Forecast area types vocabulary	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P29/current/6	SKOS	Climate and Forecast (CF) area types vocabulary.	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.
P31	Climate and Forecast Attribute Names	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P31/current/	SKOS	Terms used to define the recognised metadata attributes for the description of CF-compliant data stored in NetCDF files.	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.
P37	Climate and Forecast Calendars	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P37/current/	SKOS	Terms to describe the calendar systems used for time coordinates in CF-compliant data files	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.
P15	Climate and Forecast Cell Methods	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P15/current/	SKOS	Terms used to describe measured phenomena derivation algorithms, primarily targeted at statistical parameters.	to be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.
P30	Climate and Forecast Standardized Region Names	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P30/current/	SKOS	Terms used to label regions of the Earth's Surface or their representation in a numerical simulation in the CF metadata conventions for data stored in NetCDF	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.
P38	Climate and Forecast Vertical Coordinate Coverages	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P38/current/	SKOS	Terms used by the CF community to describe the data coverage over the vertical (z) coordinate.	To be ingested after problems with P07 have been solved.

Table 8: Suggested Climate and Forecast Conventions Vocabularies, which have not yet been ingested to the ESS collection